

Supplemental Material from

Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease alters differently fatty acid profiles in the liver and adipose tissue

Table of Contents

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Figure 4

Supplementary Figure 5

Supplementary Figure 6

Supplementary Figure 7

Supplementary Figure 8

Supplementary Figure 9

Supplementary Figure 10

Supplementary Figure 11

Supplementary Figure 12

Supplementary Figure 13

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1

Supplementary Table 2

Supplementary Figure 1 A Venn diagram representing the overlap of samples from different tissue depots and serum. SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 2. Levels of (a) polyunsaturated fatty acids, (b) saturated fatty acids, (c) monounsaturated fatty acids and (d) estimated enzyme activities in serum, subcutaneous adipose tissue, visceral adipose tissue and liver in patients with a normal liver, simple steatosis, and MASH. The values are scaled. The Kruskal-Wallis test was used to test difference between patients with a normal liver, simple steatosis, and MASH. If the Kruskal-Wallis test yielded a significant result, the Dunn test was applied for post hoc multiple comparisons. * indicates a significant difference between individuals with normal liver and those with MASH; § between those with steatosis and MASH; and # between those with normal liver and steatosis in Dunn test. Statistical significance was defined as false discovery rate (FDR) of <0.05. DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, MASH; metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 3. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in a linear model adjusted with age, sex, BMI and diabetes status. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 4. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in linear model adjusted with age, sex, BMI, diabetes status, serum insulin, glucose, cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol and TG levels. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and FDR<0.05 was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, HDL; high density lipoprotein, LDL; low density lipoprotein, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SFA; saturated fatty acid, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, TG; triglyceride, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 5. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in a linear model adjusted with age, sex, BMI and *PNPLA3* rs738409. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, *PNPLA3*; patatin-like phospholipase domain containing 3, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 6. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in a linear model adjusted with age, sex and *MBOAT7* rs641738. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, *MBOAT7*; membrane bound O-acetyltransferase 7, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 7. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in a linear model adjusted with age, sex and *TM6SF2* rs58542926. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, *TM6SF2*; trans-membrane 6 superfamily 2, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 8. Results of a linear model adjusted with age, sex, BMI, *PNPLA3* rs738409, *TM6SF2* rs58542926, *MBOAT7* rs641738 demonstrating differences in fatty acid and estimated enzyme levels in relation to liver phenotypes in different tissues. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, *MBOAT7*; membrane bound O-acetyltransferase 7, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, *PNPLA3*; patatin-like phospholipase domain containing 3, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, *TM6SF2*; trans-membrane 6 superfamily 2, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 9. Results of a linear model adjusted with age and sex demonstrating differences in fatty acid and estimated enzyme levels in relation to *PNPLA3* rs738409 genotype in different tissues. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, *PNPLA3*; patatin-like phospholipase domain containing 3, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 10. Results of a linear model adjusted with age and sex demonstrating differences in fatty acid and estimated enzyme levels in relation to *MBOAT7* rs641738 genotype in different tissues. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and FDR<0.05 was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosaehaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, *MBOAT7*; membrane bound O-acetyltransferase 7, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 11. Results of a linear model adjusted with age and sex demonstrating differences in fatty acid and estimated enzyme levels in relation to *TM6SF2* rs58542926 genotype in different tissues. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, *TM6SF2*; trans-membrane 6 superfamily 2, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 12. Results of a linear model adjusted with use of lipid-lowering medication, age and sex demonstrating differences in fatty acid and estimated enzyme levels in relation to liver phenotypes in different tissues. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and $FDR < 0.05$ was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, SFA; saturated fatty acid, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Figure 13. A forest plot representing levels differences in fatty acids and estimated enzyme activities in in different tissues in relation to liver phenotype in linear model adjusted with age, sex, BMI, use of statin medication, diabetes status, serum insulin, glucose, cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol and TG levels. p-values were adjusted with false discovery rate correction and FDR<0.05 was considered significant. Statistically significant FDR-values are displayed red and insignificant are blue. BMI; body mass index, DHA; docosahexaenoic acid, DPA; docosapentaenoic acid, EPA; eicosapentaenoic acid, FDR; false discovery rate, HDL; high density lipoprotein, LDL; low density lipoprotein, MUFA; monounsaturated fatty acid, PUFA; polyunsaturated fatty acid, SAT; subcutaneous adipose tissue, SFA; saturated fatty acid, SCD1; stearoyl-CoA desaturase 1, TG; triglyceride, VAT; visceral adipose tissue

Supplementary Table 1

	SAT n=76	normal liver n=39	steatosis n=16	MASH n=21	VAT n=77	normal liver n=40	steatosis n=16	MASH n=21	Serum n=95	normal liver n=40	steatosis n=25	MASH n=30	Liver n=124	normal liver n=69	steatosis n=24	MASH n=31
sex F/%	47/61.8%	27/69.2%	9/56.3%	11/52.4%	47/61.0%	27/67.5%	9/56.3%	11/52.4%	62/65.3%	25/62.5%	20/80.0%	17/56.7%	83/66.9%	51/73.9%	16/66.7%	16/51.6%
age (years)	47.68±5.77	45.46±10.72	47.25±6.82	51.95±8.77	47.81±9.77	45.81±10.73	47.25±6.82	51.95±8.77	46.23±9.30	45.98±9.94	45.68±8.59	47.03±9.25	47.05±10.13	44.94±10.43	47.13±8.61	51.68±9.30*
BMI	43.29±5.41	42.68±5.32	42.88±3.37	44.73±6.66	43.16±5.49	42.45±5.45	42.88±3.37	44.73±6.66	44.33±6.32	43.64±7.18	44.78±4.84	44.87±6.29	43.08±5.50	42.55±5.42	43.38±4.99	44.01±6.09
fasting glucose	6.22±1.28	5.78±0.74	5.97±0.74	7.19±1.83*	6.22±1.27	5.81±0.73	5.99±0.74	7.19±1.83*	6.41±1.78	5.99±0.81	6.50±2.27	6.90±2.15	6.39±1.74	5.94±1.31	6.14±0.97	7.57±2.41*§
fasting insulin	16.66±10.13	13.99±6.83	18.59±10.92	20.06±13.31	16.71±10.07	14.15±6.81	18.59±10.92	20.06±13.31	21.99±29.46	14.71±6.79	19.12±10.43	34.08±49.29*	17.42±11.62	14.49±7.43	18.65±11.08	23.75±16.28*
ALT	42.27±32.64	34.87±19.34	41.88±21.65	55.95±50.97	41.93±21.55	34.41±19.29	41.88±21.65	55.95±50.97	46.79±31.14	38.48±23.76	39.67±17.54	63.37±45.73*§	41.53±28.48	35.15±21.94	46.46±34.45	51.71±31.09*
total cholesterol	4.11±0.97	4.08±0.83	4.25±1.23	4.07±1.10	4.11±0.96	4.07±0.82	4.25±1.23	4.07±1.10	4.31±1.01	4.10±0.84	4.06±0.85	4.78±1.20*§	4.09±0.86	4.12±0.78	4.23±1.00	3.90±0.92
LDL-cholesterol	2.35±0.89	2.35±0.77	2.43±1.00	2.25±1.02	2.35±0.88	2.36±0.76	2.43±1.00	2.25±1.02	2.50±0.85	2.42±0.77	2.27±0.75	2.82±0.97	2.29±0.79	2.33±0.71	2.46±0.96	2.09±0.81
HDL-cholesterol	1.07±0.28	1.09±0.30	1.02±0.16	1.09±0.33	1.07±0.28	1.09±0.29	1.02±0.16	1.09±0.33	1.04±0.29	1.03±0.26	1.03±0.19	1.06±0.39	1.12±0.28	1.15±0.29	1.06±0.18	1.11±0.32
triglycerides	1.51±0.59	1.38±0.49	1.74±0.75	1.99±0.59	1.51±0.59	1.38±0.48	1.74±0.75	1.99±0.59	1.63±0.71	1.42±0.51	1.68±0.67	1.88±0.88*	1.48±0.60	1.39±0.58	1.88±0.67	1.55±0.53
diabetes (n/%)	26/34.2%	9/23.1%	4/25.0%	13/61.9%*§	27/35.1%	10/25.0%	4/25.0%	13/61.9%*§	32/33.7%	11/27.5%	8/32.0%	13/43.3%	40/32.3%	10/14.5%	7/29.2%	23/74.2%*§
cholesterol medication (n/%)	25/32.9%	14/35.9%	3/18.8%	8/38.1%	25/32.5%	14/35.0%	3/18.8%	8/38.1%	25/26.3%	11/27.5%	5/20.0%	9/30.0%	41/33.3%	19/27.9%	4/16.7%	18/58.1%*§

Clinical characteristics of patients, who had subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT), visceral adipose tissue (VAT), serum or liver tissue available for this study. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables, while the Kruskal-Wallis test was used for continuous variables. If the Kruskal-Wallis test yielded a significant result, the Dunn test was applied for post hoc multiple comparisons. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. * indicates a significant difference between individuals with normal liver and those with MASH; § between those with steatosis and MASH; and # between those with normal liver and steatosis in Dunn test. ALT; alanine transferase, BMI; body mass index, HDL; high density lipoprotein, LDL; low density lipoprotein, MASH; metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis

Supplementary Table 2

	SAT#76	normal liver	steatosis	MASH#21	P-value	F-FDR	P Normal liver vs MASH	P MASH liver vs steatosis	P Steatosis vs MASH	VAT#77	normal liver	steatosis	MASH#21	P-value	P-FDR	P Normal liver vs MASH	P Normal liver vs steatosis	P Steatosis vs MASH
Saturated fatty acids SFA	29.00±2.97	29.79±2.92	29.74±2.89	29.98±3.12	0.97	0.98				28.71±3.12	28.88±2.25	27.84±2.53	29.06±3.27	0.35	0.50			
Myristic acid (14:0)	3.04±0.47	3.18±0.53	2.97±0.45	2.83±0.29	0.01	0.04*				3.14±0.61	3.31±0.68	3.06±0.56	2.87±0.36	0.01	0.04*	0.0112	0.227	0.227
Pentadecanoic acid (15:0)	0.30±0.06	0.31±0.07	0.27±0.08	0.29±0.04	0.25	0.42		0.234	0.293	0.30±0.06	0.30±0.07	0.29±0.07	0.29±0.03	0.53	0.65			
Palmitic acid (16:0)	23.30±2.00	23.08±1.89	23.39±1.94	23.47±2.28	0.61	0.70				22.02±2.14	21.80±2.07	21.58±1.43	22.80±2.58	0.18	0.31			
Heptadecanoic acid (17:0)	0.13±0.04	0.13±0.04	0.18±0.05	0.20±0.04	0.96	0.98				0.19±0.04	0.19±0.04	0.17±0.04	0.19±0.04	0.30	0.45			
Stearic acid (18:0)	2.96±0.81	2.97±0.85	2.90±0.70	3.00±0.86	0.98	0.98				3.07±0.87	3.28±0.95	2.76±0.70	2.92±0.73	0.11	0.20			
Monounsaturated fatty acids MUFA	37.11±5.15	37.34±2.99	37.04±3.29	36.75±3.45	0.85	0.93				36.76±3.11	36.84±3.17	36.55±2.37	36.17±3.50	0.61	0.70			
Palmitoleic acid (16:1 n-7)	6.35±1.73	6.26±1.70	6.42±1.37	6.47±2.65	0.96	0.94				6.90±1.95	6.77±1.85	7.59±1.79	6.62±2.22	0.19	0.32			
Vaccenic acid (18:1 n-7)	2.53±0.35	2.46±0.36	2.50±0.31	2.70±0.31	0.02	0.04*		0.518	0.116	2.30±0.35	2.22±0.35	2.26±0.32	2.49±0.30	0.008	0.02*	0.006	0.647	0.055
Oleic acid (18:1 n-9)	47.30±2.02	47.67±1.69	47.25±2.34	46.66±2.25	0.27	0.42				48.44±2.10	48.70±1.99	48.47±2.22	47.91±2.21	0.56	0.67			
Eicosenoic acid (20:1 n-9)	0.95±0.13	0.95±0.13	0.86±0.12	0.91±0.10	0.08	0.17				0.12±0.20	0.13±0.21	0.03±0.17	0.11±0.18	0.10	0.18			
Polysaturated fatty acids PUFA	13.01±1.98	12.93±1.96	13.22±1.85	13.29±2.32	0.90	0.96				12.52±2.09	12.26±1.84	12.81±2.02	12.77±2.30	0.70	0.79			
Total n6 fatty acids	11.03±1.57	10.92±1.55	11.24±1.54	11.08±1.69	0.82	0.56				10.66±1.62	10.47±1.51	10.98±1.63	10.78±1.85	0.57	0.67			
Total n3 fatty acids	2.05±0.58	2.01±0.47	1.98±0.53	2.19±0.78	0.57	0.67				1.86±0.50	1.81±0.45	1.83±0.56	1.99±0.52	0.32	0.32			
n6/n3 ratio	5.60±1.11	5.61±1.02	5.95±1.07	5.33±0.90	0.42	0.54				5.94±1.10	6.00±1.04	6.32±1.47	5.60±0.75	0.09	0.18			
Linoleic acid (18:2 n-6)	9.80±1.52	9.81±1.46	10.07±1.50	9.58±1.68	0.38	0.53				9.80±1.55	9.73±1.40	10.17±1.61	9.66±1.81	0.40	0.53			
Gamma-linolenic acid (18:3 n-6)	0.06±0.02	0.07±0.02	0.06±0.03	0.06±0.02	0.32	0.46				0.05±0.02	0.05±0.02	0.05±0.01	0.04±0.02	0.31	0.45			
Dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid (20:3 n-6)	0.34±0.10	0.30±0.07	0.33±0.09	0.42±0.12	0.00045	0.0020*	0.204		0.058	0.25±0.12	0.21±0.10	0.24±0.07	0.33±0.13	3.0x10 ⁻⁶	0.0044*	1.7x10⁻⁶	0.171	0.061
Arachidonic acid (20:4 n-6)	0.59±0.16	0.54±0.13	0.56±0.12	0.71±0.16	0.00084	0.0031*	0.680		0.013	0.35±0.13	0.30±0.11	0.34±0.10	0.45±0.14	1.2x10 ⁻⁷	6.5x10⁻⁶	6.6x10⁻⁶	0.183	0.096
Adrenic acid (22:4 n-6)	0.25±0.09	0.22±0.07	0.22±0.05	0.32±0.10	0.3x10 ⁻⁵	5.4x10⁻⁶	0.747		0.003	0.21±0.10	0.19±0.08	0.19±0.06	0.29±0.12	6.7x10 ⁻⁶	0.0027*	5.5x10⁻⁶	0.678	0.011
Docosapentaenoic acid (DPA) (22:5 n-3)	0.46±0.20	0.43±0.16	0.41±0.16	0.55±0.26	0.09	0.18				0.40±0.18	0.36±0.17	0.36±0.13	0.50±0.20	0.02	0.04*	0.017	0.849	0.958
α-linolenic acid (18:3 n-3)	1.09±0.27	1.12±0.24	1.09±0.28	1.05±0.31	0.30	0.18				1.05±0.29	1.06±0.25	1.09±0.36	1.00±0.29	0.55	0.66			
Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) (22:6 n-3)	0.36±0.21	0.33±0.18	0.34±0.17	0.43±0.29	0.09	0.18				0.31±0.16	0.29±0.16	0.29±0.15	0.37±0.16	0.05	0.10			
Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) (20:5 n-3)	0.15±0.06	0.14±0.06	0.14±0.06	0.16±0.07	0.29	0.45				0.19±0.05	0.19±0.05	0.19±0.04	0.12±0.03	0.03	0.08			
SCD1 16:1n7/16:0	0.28±0.09	0.28±0.09	0.28±0.08	0.28±0.11	0.96	0.98				0.32±0.11	0.32±0.11	0.36±0.10	0.30±0.13	0.17	0.31			
SCD1 18:1n7/18:0	0.94±0.36	0.92±0.40	0.92±0.30	1.06±0.73	0.68	0.76				0.83±0.30	0.76±0.31	0.88±0.26	0.92±0.30	0.08	0.16			
Delta-5-desaturase 20:4n6/20:3n6	1.81±0.47	1.85±0.45	1.79±0.43	1.76±0.49	0.50	0.62				1.89±0.42	1.92±0.39	1.80±0.42	1.63±0.51	0.40	0.58			
Delta-6-desaturase 18:3n6/18:2n6	0.006±0.002	0.007±0.003	0.006±0.003	0.006±0.002	0.44	0.56				0.005±0.002	0.005±0.002	0.005±0.001	0.005±0.002	0.19	0.32			
Elongase 18:1n7/16:1n7	0.42±0.09	0.41±0.10	0.40±0.07	0.45±0.11	0.97	0.51				0.36±0.11	0.35±0.09	0.31±0.07	0.41±0.18	0.02	0.06			
Elongase 18:0/16:0	0.13±0.03	0.13±0.03	0.12±0.02	0.13±0.03	0.97	0.98				0.14±0.03	0.15±0.04	0.13±0.03	0.13±0.02	0.02	0.04*	0.034	0.034	0.766
Serum n6	normal liver	steatosis	MASH#21							normal liver	steatosis	MASH#21						
Saturated fatty acids SFA	32.44±0.41	30.83±1.56	32.15±2.37	34.83±3.45	1.2x10 ⁻⁶	1.31x10⁻⁶	0.046	0.008	0.008	35.34±4.38	33.83±3.22	35.49±2.90	38.57±5.72	8.2x10 ⁻¹¹	5.9x10⁻⁶	8.9x10⁻⁶	0.031	0.191
Myristic acid (14:0)	1.54±0.58	1.25±0.39	1.52±0.56	1.95±0.58	3.5x10 ⁻⁶	3.1x10⁻⁶	0.052	0.012	0.012	2.18±0.69	2.13±0.69	2.13±0.59	2.33±0.77	0.31	0.46			
Pentadecanoic acid (15:0)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				0.29±0.08	0.31±0.08	0.30±0.09	0.26±0.04	9.3x10 ⁻⁶	0.0033*	0.0006	0.361	0.045
Palmitic acid (16:0)	27.93±2.27	28.96±1.41	27.72±2.10	29.40±2.61	1.1x10 ⁻⁸	6.4x10⁻⁶	0.078	0.049	0.049	28.53±3.55	27.41±2.53	28.62±2.50	30.99±4.80	7.7x10 ⁻¹¹	0.003*	0.0008	0.066	0.254
Heptadecanoic acid (17:0)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				0.21±0.06	0.21±0.06	0.21±0.06	0.21±0.05	0.90	0.96			
Stearic acid (18:0)	2.97±0.66	2.92±0.44	2.92±0.40	3.49±0.74	1.8x10 ⁻⁸	1.8x10⁻⁶	0.020	0.020	0.020	4.02±0.85	3.67±0.71	4.15±0.67	4.68±0.84	4.8x10 ⁻¹¹	6.2x10⁻⁶	3.6x10⁻⁶	0.020	0.040
Monounsaturated fatty acids MUFA	49.83±2.86	50.11±2.62	50.14±2.57	49.20±3.37	0.62	0.70				53.04±3.08	53.23±2.58	53.99±2.52	51.91±4.11	0.09	0.18			
Palmitoleic acid (16:1 n-7)	5.07±1.34	4.69±1.32	5.33±1.19	5.96±1.40	0.06	0.12				4.65±1.21	4.85±1.21	4.45±1.03	4.36±1.45	0.04	0.08			
Vaccenic acid (18:1 n-7)	2.89±0.40	2.96±0.42	3.06±0.37	3.33±0.42	0.71	0.79				2.97±0.38	2.93±0.37	2.84±0.29	2.80±0.35	0.44	0.58			
Oleic acid (18:1 n-9)	41.28±2.64	41.98±2.04	41.35±2.36	40.30±2.17	0.01	0.04*		0.206	0.242	44.93±3.19	44.82±2.52	46.13±2.76	44.25±4.42	0.14	0.25			
Eicosenoic acid (20:1 n-9)	0.48±0.08	0.48±0.07	0.46±0.07	0.52±0.09	0.04	0.08				0.60±0.16	0.65±0.15	0.56±0.17	0.51±0.10	4.9x10 ⁻¹¹	4.0x10⁻⁶	9.0x10⁻⁶	0.006	0.229
Eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) (20:5 n-3)	17.72±5.37	19.06±2.97	17.71±3.13	15.96±3.35	2.2x10 ⁻⁶	0.001*	1.2x10⁻⁶	0.106	0.048	11.62±3.00	12.94±2.49	10.52±2.28	9.52±3.06	3.9x10 ⁻⁶	0.003*	0.0008	0.066	0.182
Total n6 fatty acids	13.99±0.09	15.14±2.10	14.03±2.30	12.41±3.35	0.00008	0.00005*	4.1x10⁻⁶	0.940	0.009	10.18±2.50	11.25±2.08	9.36±1.95	8.45±2.61	1.6x10 ⁻⁷	2.4x10⁻⁶	4.2x10⁻⁶	0.001	0.187
Total n3 fatty acids	3.74±1.38	3.95±1.34	3.67±1.53	3.55±1.32	0.40	0.53				1.44±0.61	1.70±0.57	1.17±0.42	1.07±0.52	3.2x10 ⁻⁷	6.1x10⁻⁶	2.2x10⁻⁶	2.9x10⁻⁶	0.328
n6/n3 ratio	4.05±1.11	4.17±1.08	4.21±1.22	3.69±1.04	0.27	0.42				7.78±2.21	7.69±1.67	8.79±2.78	8.92±3.31	0.04	0.01*	0.014	0.018	0.949
Linoleic acid (18:2 n-6)	12.21±2.36	13.29±2.04	12.28±2.21	10.72±2.12	8.2x10 ⁻⁶	6.0x10⁻⁶	3.7x10⁻⁶	0.064	0.015	9.55±2.31	10.46±1.93	8.95±1.88	8.01±2.45	1.2x10 ⁻⁷	1.3x10⁻⁶	1.6x10⁻⁶	0.0069	0.129
Gamma-linolenic acid (18:3 n-6)	0.23±0.12	0.22±0.13	0.23±0.11	0.25±0.10	0.36	0.51				0.11±0.06	0.12±0.06	0.09±0.05	0.10±0.07	0.05	0.12			
Dihomo-gamma-linolenic acid (20:3 n-6)	0.25±0.05	0.23±0.04	0.23±0.06	0.27±0.06	0.003	0.01*	0.010	0.488	0.006	0.16±0.08	0.20±0.08	0.11±0.04	0.11±0.05	4.9x10 ⁻¹¹	2.8x10⁻⁶	2.4x10⁻⁶	2.3x10⁻⁶	0.990
Arachidonic acid (20:4 n-6)	1.30±0.48	1.41±0.50	1.30±0.42	1.16±0.46	0.09	0.18				0.36±0.20	0.47±0.19	0.21±0.08	0.23±0.12	4.7x10 ⁻¹²	5.4x10⁻⁶	3.6x10⁻⁶	3.1x10⁻⁶	0.566
Adrenic acid (22:4 n-6)	NA	NA	NA</															